

Effect of *Prosopis juliflora* and *Ziziphus joazeiro* plant extracts on *Stethorus tridens* predatory behaviour on *Tetranychus bastosi*

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Abstract

Stethorini are unique among Coccinellidae and specifically prey on mites, particularly on Tetranychidae. Furthermore, they are commonly used in biological control programs in several regions around the world. Here, the selectivity of LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ aqueous extracts of *Prosopis juliflora* L. and *Ziziphus joazeiro* Mart. estimated for the pest mite *Tetranychus bastosi* Tuttle, Baker et Sales (Acari Tetranychidae), was assessed for its effects on the predator *Stethorus tridens* Gordon (Coleoptera Coccinellidae). The effect of the extracts used as a preventive or as a curative treatment on the predation of *S. tridens* on *T. bastosi*, and the repellent effect on larvae and adults of the predator were evaluated. Phenolic compounds present in each extract were analysed. LC₅₀ of the *P. juliflora* extract did not affect the predation of *S. tridens* on *T. bastosi*. Conversely, LC₉₀ of this extract, as well as LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ of the *Z. joazeiro* extract significantly reduced prey consumption rate of *T. bastosi* by the predator. LC₉₀ of both extracts repelled *S. tridens* larvae, whereas only that of the *P. juliflora* extract caused repellency in adult predators. Significant levels of gallic acid and caffeic acid were found in the *P. juliflora* extract, while in the *Z. joazeiro* extract, gallic acid was identified in significant quantities mainly at LC₉₀. The *P. juliflora* extract was selective to *S. tridens* when used at LC₅₀, which may enable the use of this extract together with *S. tridens* for integrated management of *T. bastosi*.

Key words: Stethorini, alternative control, physic nut, mite, integrated pest management.

Introduction

Coccinellidae (Coleoptera) comprise a group of predators that are important agents in the biological control of various agricultural pests (He *et al.*, 2020). The tribe Stethorini is represented by predators of the genera *Stethorus* Weise and *Parastethorus* Pang et Mao, which are specialized in the consumption of phytophagous mites, with a particular preference for Tetranychidae. Ladybugs of the genus *Stethorus* have a wide geographical distribution. They are commonly used in biological control programs for Tetranychidae because of their high predatory potential, as they can consume large numbers of mites at different life stages (Biddinger *et al.*, 2009; Costa *et al.*, 2020).

In Brazil, Costa *et al.* (2017) recorded the presence of the predator *Stethorus tridens* Gordon, associated with the phytophagous mite *Tetranychus bastosi* Tuttle, Baker et Sales (Acari Tetranychidae) in physic nut (*Jatropha curcas* L.) plantations in the semiarid region of Pernambuco. The authors evaluated the functional response of the predator and verified a daily consumption of approximately 50 *T. bastosi* individuals, thus demonstrating its potential for the control of this particular pest.

Currently, control of *T. bastosi* is achieved with synthetic acaricides that are not registered with the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply (MAPA, 2003). Therefore, methods are urgently required that can be used as an alternative to such synthetic products. Furthermore, studies have shown that plant extracts may have a certain potential to combat *T. bastosi* (Xavier *et al.*, 2015; Ferraz *et al.*, 2017; Santos *et al.*, 2019). However, there is a lack of research available focused on evaluating the selectivity of plant extracts to the natural enemies of *T. bastosi*, such as *S. tridens*.

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate whether the extracts of *Prosopis juliflora* (Sw) DC. (Mesquite) and *Ziziphus joazeiro* Mart. (Juazeiro) (used at LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ for *T. bastosi*) are selective to *S. tridens*. The scope of this study was to determine whether the use of these extracts can be combined with that of coccinellids for an effective control of the mite pest.

Materials and methods

Rearing of *T. bastosi* and *S. tridens*

The initial populations *T. bastosi* and *S. tridens* were obtained from an experimental area located at the Academic Unit of Serra Talhada (UAST/UFRPE), Serra Talhada, Pernambuco at 07°59'31"S 38°17'54"W, at an elevation of 429 m a.s.l.

Once in the laboratory, *T. bastosi* individuals were kept in Gerbox® boxes (12 × 12 × 5 cm) containing 4-cm thick polyethylene foam inside. This foam was covered with filter paper on which a leaf of jack bean *Canavalia ensiformis* (L.) DC. (Fabaceae) was placed with its adaxial surface facing down. The foam was moistened with distilled water as required to maintain full leaf turgidity. Hydrophilic cotton moistened in distilled water was placed around the leaf to prevent mites from escaping. As leaves lost turgidity, they were replaced with new ones.

Rearing of the predator was performed as previously reported by Costa *et al.* (2017), using plastic containers (11.0 × 11.0 × 3.0 cm) containing a *T. bastosi*-infested leaf of jack bean (*C. ensiformis*) attached by the petiole to a glass container (5 mL) filled with water. The upper end of the plastic container was sealed with organza fabric to prevent insects from escaping. The leaf was changed every two days to maintain sufficient *T. bastosi*